

CS-NL

Citizen Science Nederland

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THE NATIONAL NETWORK
FOR EVERYONE INVOLVED
IN CITIZEN SCIENCE.

ANNUAL
REPORT

20

25

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01: CS-NL in Numbers

NEWSLETTER	890
SOCIAL MEDIA (LinkedIn)	550
KENNIS MAKEN: CS EXPO	260+
NETWORK DAY	150+
KNOWLEDGE PLATFORM	130+
COMMUNITY HUB (WORKING GROUPS)	70+

Over the past year, we have continued to grow and have managed to reach a lot of people. Whether through our newsletter, social media or at our major events such as Kennis Maken: CS Expo, there was a great deal of interest and engagement. In addition, there is a lively and enthusiastic group that actively shares knowledge and collaborates within our working groups.

Overview of participants of the Network Day

02: Community Highlights

A selection of your highlights from 2025, compiled during the CS-NL Network Day in 2026.

03: Network Day

The year got off to a good start with the 3rd CS-NL Annual Network Day on 14 January 2025 at the Neude Library in Utrecht. More than 150 participants came together to celebrate Citizen Science, make new connections and work together during workshops and working group meetings. During the Show & Tell session, participants were able to discuss projects, sensors and other Citizen Science topics.

04: Launch Knowledge Platform

During the Network Day, our knowledge platform "citizenscience.nl" was launched: a central hub for all projects, resources, organisations and platforms related to Citizen Science. Since the launch, several profiles have already been created, but still there are many profiles missing. Over the coming year, we at CS-NL will be devoting more attention to this, in particular by mapping projects and initiatives in the Netherlands. Join us and add your information on the platform!

05: Launch Community Hub

The CS-NL Community Hub was also launched during the Network Day. This hub is the place to connect with the network, share needs and engage in discussions. The hub can be found on the Just One Giant Lab (JOGL) platform and was tested in 2025 by members of the various CS-NL working groups. JOGL has been working on the feedback from the community, and a new version will be launched in 2026, which will also be open to all members of Citizen Science Nederland!

06: Support Citizen Science Hubs

In 2025, the very first Citizen Science Hubs were launched in the Netherlands, funded by Open Science NL. These hubs are linked and supported by CS-NL. Together, they are developing a learning programme to share knowledge and expertise and to learn from one another. In 2027, Open Science NL will open a new call for proposals, and a further five Citizen Science Hubs will be established. Look out for more news in our newsletter and our social media channels.

07: Kennis Maken: Citizen Science Expo

On 2 October 2025, the very first 'Kennis Maken: Citizen Science Expo' took place, organised by CS-NL, Waag Futurelab and the Association of Lecturers. More than 260 participants gathered at the Amsterdam Public Library to showcase the state of Citizen Science in the Netherlands. Participants were able to learn and explore through 21 sessions, 13 exhibition stands, 5 lightning talks, 4 interactive experiences and 3 excursions. The next Citizen Science Expo will take place in 2027.

08: Advisory Board

The CS-NL Advisory Board was officially appointed in 2025. This advisory board acts as a sounding board and actively contributes ideas regarding both the long-term development and the future-proofing of the network. In addition, the advisory board supports the network at a strategic, substantive and collaborative level.

Sicco de Knecht

Darco Jansen

Anne-Floor Scholvinck

Martijn Kleppe

Wilja Jurg

Sabine Wildevuur

Jeanet Bruil

Sarah Coombs

Tom Schuurmans

09: Working Groups

These are the CS-NL working groups. These groups form a key part of the network, as they bring members together to share knowledge and jointly develop new resources. If you would like to join one of the working groups, please contact the community manager Anouk (anouk@citizenscience.nl) or the dedicated coordinator(s) of the working group.

Current Working Groups

Citizen Science & Education

Coordinator: Willie Kerkhof - GLOBE Nederland

Citizen Science for Health & Wellbeing

Coordinator: Kris Bevelander - Radboudumc

Data & Infrastructure

Coordinator: Frank Ostermann - University of Twente

Embedding CS in Dutch research institutions

Coordinator: Maya van den Berg - Citizen Science NL

Nature & Biodiversity

Coordinator: Froukje Rienks - KNAW-NIOO

New Working Groups

Citizen Science & Policy

Coordinator: Tom Schuurmans - Ministerie I&W

Games in Citizen Science

Coordinator: Rene Luigies - Games for Health

Citizen Science & Art

Coordinator: Frans Snik & Lucas Evers - KxWxS

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